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Propagation of Elastic Waves along a Cylindrical Rod of Micropolar Elastic Solid with Stretch under Impedance Boundary Conditions

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Abstract

Objective: The objective of this article is to derive the dispersion relations of elastic waves along a cylindrical rod of homogeneous, isotropic micropolar elastic solid with stretch under impedance boundary conditions. **Method:** The basic equations and constitutive relations are converted into cylindrical coordinates and solved by adopting the method of plane harmonic solution. **Findings:** Displacements, micro rotations, and micro stretch relations are derived analytically. The dispersion relations pertaining to elastic waves with using impedance boundary conditions also derived analytically and these relations are compared with the results of Tomar. **Novelty:** With the use of the MATLAB program, the effects of impedance parameters, micropolarity and stretch are discussed for a particular model. The speed of the elastic wave is proportional to the ratio of the impedance parameter in microstretch elastic solids, but there is no significant effect of the impedance ratio in micropolar elastic solids.

Keywords: Elastic Waves; Cylindrical rod; Micropolarity; Micro stretch; Impedance Boundary Conditions

1 Introduction

An elastic disturbance that propagates in solids, liquids or gaseous medium is named an elastic wave. The waves that are formed in the earth's crust during earthquakes are a good example of elastic waves in a solid material. Ultrasonic waves, or sound waves, are also elastic waves in liquids and gases. Elastic waves are categorized by two types: longitudinal waves, or compression waves, or p-waves, and another is transversal or s-waves. The oscillations of longitudinal waves are in the direction of propagation, while transversal wave oscillations are perpendicular to the propagation of waves. To study the state of stress-strain, material properties, and structure, the elastic waves are also more effective tool.

A non-linear theory of simple micro elastic materials was formulated and developed long ago. Later on, a subclass of non-linear theory of micropolar elasticity is named as "a linear theory of micropolar elasticity". The Linear theory of micropolar elasticity is a generalization of classical theory of elasticity. The major difference between the micropolar theory of elasticity and classical theory of elasticity is the inclusion of independent "micro rotation vector". The motion is described by a displacement vector in the theory of classical elasticity. So, there are three degrees of freedom required for this theory. But in the theory of micropolar elasticity, motion is described by two types of vectors named as: displacement vector and micro rotation vector. So, this theory requires six degrees of freedom. The force at any point on the surface of a micropolar elastic solid can be categorized as a "force stress tensor and couple stress tensor". In a micro elastic material, the dumbbell - shaped particles can be uniformly distributed throughout the entire body. The micropolar elastic material is also named as "micropolar continuum". Augustine⁽¹⁾ applied the harmonic method of wave analysis to derive reflected and transmitted waves at an interface of micropolar fiber-reinforced and liquid. Now-a-days, the theory of micropolar elasticity is utilized to examine the deformation properties of cellular solids, polymers, bones, granular materials, composite fibrous materials, masonry, etc. Also, this theory is applicable to explain the long - range interactions and microscopic motion in various types of solids. This theory is also associated with all engineering practical problems.

The directors of the body contained only "breathing-type micro-deformations", known as micro -stretch continuum. In the micro-stretch continuum, the material points can be independently stretched and contracted by their rotation and translations. The theory of micro-stretch elasticity is a special case of micro-morphic theory and a generalization of the theory of micropolar elasticity. This theory eliminates the steps between experimental and classical elasticity because, classical elasticity does not present acceptable results when the effect of material microstructure was known on the body's overall deformations. Some of the authors, Neetu Rani⁽²⁾, and Adina Chirila⁽³⁾, dedicated their research to the fields of microstretch elastic solids and derived the stretch dependent plane waves in thermo elastic diffusion medium. Lofty and Bary⁽⁴⁾ studied the effect of micro stretch and rotation on thermal elastic waves under photo thermal excitation. With the principle of mechanics, the field equations are solved for homogeneous, isotropic micro stretch and void elastic mediums, and the effect of micro stretch and voids on plane wave propagation was discussed by Singh D, Garg M, and Tomar SK⁽⁵⁾. The effects of micro stretch and micro- voids on plane waves in a generalized thermo - micro - stretch elastic solid containing voids was derived by Manish G, Singh D, and Tomar SK⁽⁶⁾, and they found that coupled longitudinal waves exist with non-negative frequencies and are influenced by micro stretch and micro voids, but coupled transverse waves exist with some cut-off frequency.

Now-a-days, the demand for the analysis of computations of systems with moving boundaries has increasing, which is becoming more complicated. The boundary conditions are very essential in the fields of Physics, Engineering, and electro-magnetism for solving the equations of current voltage and strengths on surfaces and closed paths. The boundary conditions are also needed for different problems because the conditions on the boundary between two areas change. The impedance is the measure of the opposition to the electric field. Impedance opposes the flow of alternate current, but resistance opposes the flow of both types of current, named AC and DC. The boundary conditions, which are linear combinations of unknown functions and the derivatives of those unknown functions on the boundary, are named "impedance boundary conditions". These conditions are related to acoustic velocity acoustic pressure to each other at any point. The impedance boundary conditions are commonly used in the fields of electromagnetism and acoustics, but not in geophysics or seismology. A few literature available on using of impedance boundary conditions on wave propagation. Kersten Schmidt⁽⁷⁾ discussed wave propagation with the use of impedance boundary conditions. Somaiah⁽⁸⁾ studied the rotation and initial stress effects on Love wave propagation subject to impedance boundary conditions.

A few authors looked at the plane and surface wave propagation in a micropolar elastic solid with varying stretch effects. It has not yet been used to apply the idea of elastic waves along the cylindrical rod under impedance boundary conditions. Therefore, in the presence of impedance boundary conditions, the dispersion relations for elastic waves along a cylindrical rod of micropolar elastic solid with stretch are derived in this work. For a certain material, the important impacts of micropolarity, microstretch, and impedance characteristics on the dispersion relation of elastic waves are examined.

This article is arranged as an introduction in Section 1, methodology is given in Section 2, results and discussion are given in Section 3, and finally an overall conclusion is given in Section 4.

2 Methodology

The relations of macro displacement, micro rotation for a homogeneous, isotropic elastic solid with stretch of infinite extent in the absence of body forces and body couples are considered by Somaiah and Ravi Kumar⁽⁹⁾ as follows:

$$(\lambda + \mu)\text{grad}(\text{div}\vec{U}) + (\mu + K)\nabla^2\vec{U} + K\text{curl}\vec{W} = \rho\frac{\partial^2\vec{U}}{\partial t^2} \quad (1)$$

$$K \text{curl } \vec{U} + \gamma \nabla^2 \vec{W} + (\alpha + \beta) \text{grad}(\text{div} \vec{W}) - 2K \vec{W} = \rho J \frac{\partial^2 \vec{W}}{\partial t^2} \tag{2}$$

$$\alpha_0 \nabla^2 \Phi^* - \eta_0 \Phi^* = \frac{\rho J}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi^*}{\partial t^2} \tag{3}$$

The constitutive relations of the stress tensor τ_{ji} , couple stress tensor M_{ji} and micro stress tensor λ_j^* given by

$$\tau_{ji} = \lambda U_{i,l} \delta_{ij} + \mu (U_{i,j} + U_{j,i}) - K (\epsilon_{lji} W_l - U_{i,j}) \tag{4}$$

$$M_{ji} = \beta_0 \epsilon_{lji} \Phi^*_{,l} + \alpha W_{l,i} \delta_{ij} + \beta W_{j,i} + \gamma W_{i,j} \tag{5}$$

$$\lambda_j^* = \alpha_0 \Phi^*_{,j} + \frac{\beta_0}{3} \epsilon_{ijl} W_{l,i} \tag{6}$$

where the details of various symbols in Equations (1), (2), (3), (4), (5) and (6) are given in the following table.

Table 1. Parameters

Symbol	Name
λ, μ	Lame's constants
K	Elastic constant
α, β, γ	Micropolar constants
α_0, η_0	Micro stretch moduli
ρ	Mass density of the solid
J	Micro inertia
\vec{U}	Macro displacement vector
\vec{W}	Micro rotation vector
Φ^*	Micro stretch scalar
δ_{ij}	Kronecker's delta
ϵ_{lji}	Permutation symbol

The dilation vector e_{mn} and macro displacement vector \vec{U} are related as $e_{mn} = \frac{1}{2} (U_{m,n} + U_{n,m})$, where the suffix comma indicates the partial derivative with respect to corresponding Cartesian coordinate.

Consider a homogeneous, isotropic micropolar with stretch cylindrical rod of infinite extent having radius r . For purely sinusoidal and axial symmetric wave propagation along the axial direction of the cylinder, consider cylindrical polar coordinates (r, θ, z) at any point on the surface of cylinder and z -axis being pointing upwards into the cylinder. So, for axi-symmetric problem, assume that the displacement vector \vec{U} and micro rotational vector \vec{W} as $\vec{U} = (U_r, 0, U_z)$ and $\vec{W} = (0, W_\theta, 0)$, where radial displacement component, circumferential displacement component and axial displacement component respectively U_r, U_θ and U_z are given as $U_r = U_r(r, z), U_\theta = 0, U_z = U_z(r, \theta)$ and the micro rotational components $W_r = W_z = 0; W_\theta = W(r, z)$ with, $\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} () = 0$. From the above consideration, Equations (1), (2) and (3) becomes,

$$(\lambda + 2\mu + K) (U_{r,rr} + r^{-1} U_{r,r} - r^{-2} U_r) + (\mu + K) U_{r,zz} + (\lambda + \mu) U_{z,rz} - K W_{,z} = \rho \ddot{U}_r \tag{7}$$

$$(\mu + K) (U_{z,rr} + r^{-1} U_{z,r}) + (\lambda + 2\mu + K) U_{z,zz} + (\lambda + \mu) (r^{-1} U_{r,z} + U_{r,zr}) + K (W_{,r} + r^{-1} W) = \rho \ddot{U}_z \tag{8}$$

$$\gamma (W_{,rr} + r^{-1} W_{,r} - r^{-2} W + W_{,zz}) - 2KW + K (U_{r,z} - U_{z,r}) = \rho J \ddot{W} \tag{9}$$

$$\alpha_0 (\Phi_{,rr}^* + r^{-1}\Phi_{,r}^* + \Phi_{,zz}^*) - \eta_0\Phi^* = \frac{\rho J}{2}\ddot{\Phi}^* \tag{10}$$

where the suffix comma indicates partial derivative with respect to corresponding coordinate axes and super posed double dot indicates second order partial derivative with respect to time t .

Now, Equations (4), (5) and (6) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{rr} &= \lambda \nabla \cdot \vec{U} + (2\mu + K)U_{r,r} \\ &= \lambda (U_{r,r} + r^{-1}U_r + U_{z,z}) + (2\mu + K)U_{r,r} \\ &= (\lambda + 2\mu + K)U_{r,r} + \lambda (r^{-1}U_r + U_{z,z}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{zz} &= \lambda (U_{r,r} + r^{-1}U_r) + (\lambda + 2\mu + K)U_{z,z} \\ \tau_{rz} &= \mu (U_{r,z} + U_{z,r}) + K (U_{z,r} + W) \\ M_{r\theta} &= \gamma W_{,r} + \beta_0 \Phi_{,z}^* \end{aligned}$$

$$\lambda_r^* = \alpha_0 \Phi_{,r}^* - \frac{\beta_0}{3} W_{,z} \tag{11}$$

Fig 1. Problem Model

After introducing Helmholtz scalar potential S , vector potential \vec{V} with $\vec{V} = (V_r, V_\theta, V_z)$, the displacement vector \vec{U} converted as

$$\vec{U} = \text{grad}S + \text{curl}\vec{V}; \text{div}\vec{V} = 0$$

Inserting $\vec{U} = (U_r, 0, U_z)$ and $V_r = V_r(r, \theta, z)$, $V_\theta = V_\theta(r, \theta, z)$; $V_z = V_z(r, \theta, z)$ in above equation, one can obtain,

$$(U_r, 0, U_z) = \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial r}, \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial S}{\partial \theta}, \frac{\partial S}{\partial z} \right) + \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial V_z}{\partial \theta} - \frac{\partial V_\theta}{\partial z}, \frac{\partial V_r}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial V_z}{\partial r}, \frac{\partial V_\theta}{\partial r} + r^{-1}V_\theta - r^{-1} \frac{\partial V_r}{\partial \theta} \right)$$

But $\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta}(\) = 0$ and setting $V_\theta = V$, we obtain the components U_r, U_z as

$$U_r = \frac{\partial S}{\partial r} - \frac{\partial V}{\partial z}; U_z = \frac{\partial S}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial r} + \frac{V}{r} \tag{12}$$

On using Equation (12), the Equations (7), (8), (9) and (10) reduces to

$$(\nabla^2 - r^{-2})S - \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial r \partial z} = \frac{\rho}{(\lambda + 2\mu + K)} \frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial t^2} \tag{13}$$

$$\nabla^2 V + (\mu + K)r^{-1} \frac{\partial V}{\partial r} + \left(\frac{\lambda + 2\mu + K}{\mu + K} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial r \partial z} + r^{-1} \frac{\partial S}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{K}{\mu + K} W = \frac{\rho}{\mu + K} \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial t^2} \tag{14}$$

$$(\nabla^2 - r^{-2})W - \frac{K}{\gamma} (\nabla^2 - r^{-2})V - \frac{2K}{\gamma} W = \frac{\rho J}{\gamma} \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial t^2} \tag{15}$$

$$\nabla^2 \Phi^* - \frac{\eta_0}{\alpha_0} \Phi^* = \frac{\rho J}{2\alpha_0} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi^*}{\partial t^2} \tag{16}$$

where $\nabla^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2}$.

Solutions of Equations (13), (14), (15) and (16) for unattenuated wave propagation in the direction of z -axis are:

$$[S, V, W, \Phi^*] = [A_1 J_1(\zeta r), A_0 J_0(\xi r), B_1 J_1(\xi r), B_0 J_0(\chi r)] e^{i(\omega t - qz)} \tag{17}$$

where q, ω are angular wave number and angular frequency, and they are connected with phase velocity c by $c = \frac{\omega}{q}$ and $J_0(), J_1()$ are Bessel functions of first kind of order zero and order one respectively.

After inserting Equation (17), the Equations (13), (14), (15) and (16) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} S &= A_1 J_1(\zeta r) e^{i(\omega t - qz)} \\ W &= [B_1 J_1(\xi_1 r) + B'_1 J_1(\xi_2 r)] e^{i(\omega t - qz)} \\ V &= [A_0 J_0(\xi_1 r) + A'_0 J_0(\xi_2 r)] e^{i(\omega t - qz)} \\ \Phi^* &= B_0 J_0(\chi r) e^{i(\omega t - qz)} \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

where $\zeta^2 = q^2 - \frac{\rho \omega^2}{(\lambda + 2\mu + K)}$; $\chi^2 = q^2 - \frac{\rho J \omega^2}{2\alpha_0} + \frac{\eta_0}{\alpha_0}$; $\xi_{1,2}^2 = \frac{1}{2} \left[-a \pm (a^2 + 4b)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]$

$$a = \frac{\rho J \omega^2}{\gamma} + \frac{\rho \omega^2 + iq\zeta(\lambda + 2\mu + K) + K}{(\mu + K)}$$

$$b = q^2 \left[\rho \omega^2 \left(\frac{J}{\gamma} + \frac{1}{(\mu + K)} + \frac{K}{(\mu + K)} \right) \right] - \rho \omega^2 \left[\frac{J}{\gamma} + \frac{1}{(\mu + K)} \right]$$

$A_0, A'_0, B_1, B'_1, A_1, B_0$ are arbitrary constants and related as

$$(A_0, A'_0) = \frac{-\gamma}{K} \left(1 + \frac{\rho J \omega^2}{\xi_1^2 - q^2}, 1 + \frac{\rho J \omega^2}{\xi_2^2 - q^2} \right) (B_1, B'_1) \tag{19}$$

Now the displacement components U_r and U_z are given by

$$U_r = [iq \{A_0 J_0(\xi_1 r) + A'_0 J_0(\xi_2 r)\} + A_1 \zeta J'_1(\zeta r)] e^{i(\omega t - qz)} \tag{20}$$

and

$$U_z = \left\{ -iq J_1(\zeta r) A_1 + [\xi_1 J'_0(\xi_1 r) + r^{-1} J_0(\xi_1 r)] A_0 + [\xi_2 J'_0(\xi_2 r) + r^{-1} J_0(\xi_2 r)] A'_0 \right\} e^{i(\omega t - qz)} \tag{21}$$

2.1 Boundary Conditions and Secular equations

Malischewsky⁽¹⁰⁾, Godoy E, Duran M, Nedelec JC⁽¹¹⁾ stated the following impedance boundary conditions:

$$\tau_{ij} + \omega Z_i U_i = 0; i, j = r, \theta, z \tag{22}$$

where Z_i are impedance real parameters with dimensions stress/velocity and angular frequency ω is given by $\omega = qc$, with q is a wave number and C is the phase velocity. By Equation (22), the boundary conditions of stretch - dependent elastic wave propagation in micropolar elastic solid at $r = r_1$ are given by-

$$\tau_{rr} + \omega Z_r U_r = 0; \tau_{rz} + \omega Z_z U_z = 0; M_{r\theta} = 0; \lambda_r^* = 0$$

or, equivalently

$$\tau_{rr} + \omega Z_1 U_r = \tau_{rz} + \omega Z_3 U_z = 0$$

$$M_{r\theta} = \lambda_r^* = 0 \text{ at } r = r_1 \tag{23}$$

with the help of Equations (11) and (21), the Equation (23) reduces to the following system of homogeneous equations in B_1, B_1', A_1, B_0

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[(\lambda + 2\mu + K)iq\xi_1 J_0'(\xi_1 r_1) - \lambda iq\xi_1 J_0'(\xi_1 r_1) + \omega Z_1 iq J_0(\xi_1 r_1) \right] a_1 B_1 + \\ & \left[(\lambda + 2\mu + K)iq\xi_2 J_0'(\xi_2 r_1) - \lambda iq\xi_2 J_0'(\xi_2 r_1) + \omega Z_1 iq J_0(\xi_2 r_1) \right] a_2 B_1' + \\ & \left[(\lambda + 2\mu + K)iq\zeta^2 J_1''(\zeta r_1) + \lambda r_1^{-1} \zeta J_1'(\zeta r_1) - \lambda q^2 J_1(\zeta r_1) + \omega Z_1 \zeta J_1'(\zeta r_1) \right] A_1 = 0 \\ & \left[\mu q^2 J_0(\xi_1 r_1) + \mu \xi_1^2 J_0''(\xi_1 r_1) + r_1^{-1} \mu \xi_1 J_0'(\xi_1 r_1) + K \xi_1^2 J_0'(\xi_1 r_1) + K \xi_1 r_1^{-1} J_0'(\xi_1 r_1) + \right. \\ & \quad \left. \omega Z_2 \xi_1 J_0'(\xi_1 r_1) + \omega Z_2 r_1^{-1} J_0(\xi_1 r_1) + K a_1^{-1} J_1(\xi_1 r_1) \right] a_1 B_1 \\ & + \left[\mu q^2 J_0(\xi_2 r_1) + \mu \xi_2^2 J_0''(\xi_2 r_1) + r_1^{-1} \mu \xi_2 J_0'(\xi_2 r_1) + K \xi_2^2 J_0'(\xi_2 r_1) + K \xi_2 r_1^{-1} J_0'(\xi_2 r_1) + \right. \\ & \quad \left. \omega Z_2 \xi_2 J_0'(\xi_2 r_1) + \omega Z_2 r_1^{-1} J_0(\xi_2 r_1) + K a_2^{-1} J_1(\xi_2 r_1) \right] a_2 B_1' \\ & - \left[(2\mu + K)iq J_1'(\zeta r_1) + \omega Z_2 iq J_1(\zeta r_1) \right] A_1 = 0 \\ & \gamma \xi_1 J_1'(\xi_1 r_1) B_1 + \gamma \xi_2 J_1'(\xi_2 r_1) B_1' - iq \beta_0 J_0(\chi r_1) B_0 = 0 \\ & iq \frac{\beta_0}{3} J_1(\xi_1 r_1) B_1 + iq \frac{\beta_0}{3} J_1(\xi_2 r_1) B_1' + \alpha_0 \chi J_0'(\chi r_1) B_0 = 0 \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

where

$$a_j = \frac{-\gamma}{K} \left[1 + \frac{\rho \omega^2 J}{(\xi_j^2 - q^2)} \right]; j = 1, 2 \tag{25}$$

The condition for the homogeneous system (Equation (24)) has a non-trivial solution, that is:

$$\det(b_{ij}) = 0; \text{ for } i, j = 1, 2, 3, 4 \tag{26}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} b_{1j} &= \left[(2\mu + K)iq\xi_j J_0'(\xi_j r_1) + iq\omega Z_1 J_0(\xi_j r_1) \right] a_j; j = 1, 2; \\ b_{13} &= -\lambda q^2 J_1(\zeta r_1) + (\lambda r_1^{-1} + \omega Z_1) \zeta J_1'(\zeta r_1) + (\lambda + 2\mu + K)iq\zeta^2 J_1''(\zeta r_1); \\ b_{14} &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 b_{2j} &= \left[(\mu q^2 + r_1^{-1} \omega Z_2) J_0(\xi_j r_1) + K a_j^{-1} J_1(\xi_j r_1) + \left(\frac{\mu + K}{r_1} + \omega Z_2 \right) \xi_j J_0'(\xi_j r_1) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + (\mu + K) \xi_j^2 J_0''(\xi_j r_1) \right] a_j; \quad j = 1, 2 \\
 b_{23} &= - \left[(2\mu + K) i q J_1'(\zeta r_1) + \omega Z_2 i q J_1(\zeta r_1) \right]; \quad b_{24} = 0; \\
 b_{3j} &= \gamma \xi_j J_1'(\xi_j r_1); \quad j = 1, 2; \quad b_{33} = 0; \\
 b_{34} &= -i q \beta_0 J_0(\chi r_1); \quad b_{4j} = i q \frac{\beta_0}{3} J_1(\xi_j r_1); \quad j = 1, 2; \quad b_{43} = 0; \quad b_{44} = \alpha_0 \chi J_0'(\chi r_1)
 \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

Solving Equation (26), the following equation is obtained,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left[\lambda q^2 J_1(\zeta r_1) - L \zeta J_1'(\zeta r_1) - M i q \zeta^2 J_1''(\zeta r_1) \right] \\
 &\left[N J_0(\xi_j r_1) + \frac{K}{a_j} J_1(\xi_j r_1) - P \xi_j J_1(\xi_j r_1) - Q \xi_j^2 J_1'(\xi_j r_1) \right] \\
 &- \left[i q R J_1'(\zeta r_1) + S^* i q J_1(\zeta r_1) \right] \left[i q T^* J_0(\xi_j r_1) - i q R \xi_j J_1(\xi_j r_1) \right] \\
 &= a_j^{-1} \left[\alpha_0 \gamma \chi \xi_j J_1'(\xi_j r_1) J_0'(\chi r_1) - q^2 \frac{\beta_0^2}{3} J_0(\chi r_1) J_1(\xi_j r_1) \right]; \quad j = 1, 2
 \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

where $L = T^* + \lambda r_1^{-1}$; $M = \lambda + 2\mu + K$; $N = \mu q^2 + S^* r_1^{-1}$

$$P = S^* + (\mu + K) r_1^{-1}; \quad Q = (\mu + K); \quad R = 2\mu + K = M - \lambda; \quad S^* = \omega Z_2; \quad T^* = \omega Z_1 \tag{29}$$

Equation (28) is dispersion relation of elastic waves along a cylindrical rod, which is a function of micropolar, micro stretch, and impedance boundary parameters. For large values of the wave number qr_1 i.e., ($qr_1 \rightarrow \infty$), it approaches the dispersion relation of Rayleigh waves in a micropolar elastic half-space with stretch at a plane boundary.

2.2 Particular Cases:

Case (i) On the empty boundary (or, non-impedance boundary), $Z_1 = Z_2 = 0$ or $T^* = S^* = 0$, the Equation (28) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left[\lambda q^2 J_1(\zeta r_1) - \lambda r_1^{-1} J_1'(\zeta r_1) - M \zeta^2 J_1''(\zeta r_1) \right] \\
 &\left[\mu q^2 J_0(\xi_j r_1) + \frac{K}{a_j} J_1(\xi_j r_1) - (\mu + K) r_1^{-1} J_1(\xi_j r_1) - Q \xi_j^2 J_1'(\xi_j r_1) + \right. \\
 &\quad \left. R^2 q^2 \xi_j J_1'(\zeta r_1) J_1(\xi_j r_1) \right] \\
 &= a_j^{-1} \left[\alpha_0 \gamma \chi \xi_j J_1'(\xi_j r_1) J_1(\chi r_1) - q^2 \frac{\beta_0^2}{3} J_0(\chi r_1) J_1(\xi_j r_1) \right]; \quad j = 1, 2
 \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

which is a dispersion relation of an elastic wave in a cylindrical rod of micropolar elastic solid with stretch on the non-impedance boundary, and it coincides with the dispersion relations of Tomar⁽¹²⁾ in an empty cylindrical bore with appropriate replacements of modified Bessel arguments.

Case (ii) Under the absence of stretch, i.e., $\alpha_0 = \beta_0 = 0$, Equation (28) becomes,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left[\lambda q^2 J_1(\zeta r_1) - L \zeta J_1'(\zeta r_1) - M i q \zeta^2 J_1''(\zeta r_1) \right] \\
 &\left[N J_0(\xi_j r_1) + \frac{K}{a_j} J_1(\xi_j r_1) - P \xi_j J_1(\xi_j r_1) - Q \xi_j^2 J_1'(\xi_j r_1) \right] \\
 &= \left[R q J_1'(\zeta r_1) + S^* q J_1(\zeta r_1) \right] \left[q R \xi_j J_1(\xi_j r_1) - q T^* J_0(\xi_j r_1) \right]; \quad j = 1, 2
 \end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

Equation (31) is the dispersion relation of elastic waves along a cylindrical rod of micropolar elastic solid under impedance boundary conditions.

Case (iii) When the stretch and impedance boundary parameters are absent, i.e., $\alpha_0 = \beta_0 = Z_1 = Z_2 = 0$, the Equation (28) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\lambda q^2 J_1(\zeta r_1) - \lambda r_1^{-1} J_1'(\zeta r_1) - M \zeta^2 J_1''(\zeta r_1) \right] \\ & \left[\mu q^2 J_0(\xi_j r_1) + \frac{K}{a_j} J_1(\xi_j r_1) - (\mu + K) r_1^{-1} J_1(\xi_j r_1) \right] \\ & \quad - Q \xi_j^2 J_1'(\xi_j r_1) \\ & = -q^2 R^2 \xi_j J_1'(\zeta r_1) J_1(\xi_j r_1); j = 1, 2 \end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

Equation (32) is the dispersion relation of elastic waves along a micropolar cylindrical rod with empty boundary. Here, it is noted that the dispersion relations (Equation (31)) coincide with the dispersion relations derived by Tomar⁽¹²⁾ in an empty cylindrical bore of micropolar elastic solid with and without impedance boundary conditions, while the dispersion relations (Equation (32)) coincide with the dispersion relations of Tomar⁽¹²⁾ in a micropolar empty cylindrical bore.

3 Results and Discussion

Use the MATLAB software and the following values for the micropolarity and micro stretch parameters to examine the impact of impedance parameters, micropolarity, and stretch on the dispersion of elastic waves:

Micropolar and Micro-stretch parameters considered from Somaiah K, Ravi Kumar A⁽¹³⁾ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &= 7.583 \text{Gpa}; \mu = 6.334 \text{Gpa}; K = 14.905 \times 10^{-3} \text{Gpa or } 14.905 \text{Mpa}; \\ \rho &= 1189 \text{Kg/m}^3; J = 6.25 \times 10^{-7} \text{m}^2; \alpha = 3.688 \text{Gpa}; \gamma = 2.896 \text{N} \\ \alpha_0 &= 0.779 \times 10^{-9} \text{N}; \beta_0 = 0.5 \times 10^{-9} \text{N}; \eta_0 = 0.5 \times 10^{10} \text{N/m}^2 \end{aligned}$$

Assume that solid is of uniform radius $r_1 = 0.1\text{m}$ and at wavelength $2r_1$, the natural body frequency ω taken as $\omega = 5 \text{Hz}$.

Consider the radial impedance parameter Z_1 and axial impedance parameter Z_2 with respective ratios of $\frac{Z_1}{Z_2}$ as follows $Z_1 = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$ (randomly), $Z_2 = 2, 10, 25, 40$ (randomly) and $\frac{Z_1}{Z_2} = 0.1, 0.04, 0.03, 0.02$. The radius r_1 of the solid taken as, $r_1 = 0.1\text{m}$ (or, $r_1 = 10\text{cm}$) and the non-dimensional wave number q taken as $10 \leq q \leq 100$.

3.1 Effect of impedance ratio on micro stretch

Fig 2. Variation of Frequency versus Wave number for different Impedance ratios in Micropolar with stretch solid

Figures 2 and 3 represent the variation of the elastic wave frequency of a micropolar elastic solid with stretch versus wave number qr_1 for different impedance parameter ratios of $\frac{Z_1}{Z_2} = 0.1, 0.04, 0.03, 0.02$. It is seen in Figure 2 that the wave frequencies

Fig 3. Variation of Frequency versus Wave number for empty boundary and different Impedance ratios in Micropolar with stretch solid

disappear for all ratios of $\frac{Z_1}{Z_2}$ in the range of small wave numbers, qr_1 with $1 \leq qr_1 \leq 2$, and increases as $\frac{Z_1}{Z_2}$ increases, in the range of wave numbers qr_1 with $2 < qr_1 \leq 10$. Figure 3 illustrates that the wave frequencies vanish in the range of small wave numbers qr_1 with $1 \leq qr_1 \leq 2$ and high frequencies appear in non-impedance (empty) boundary solids rather than impedance boundary solids, also slowly increases as $\frac{Z_1}{Z_2}$ increases, in the range of wave numbers qr_1 with $2 < qr_1 \leq 10$.

3.2 Effect of impedance ratio on micro polarity

The variation of wave frequency versus wave number qr_1 for a micropolar elastic solid with different values of impedance ratios $\frac{Z_1}{Z_2}$ and empty boundary is shown in Figures 4 and 5, respectively. From these figures, it is seen that the wave frequencies approach zero in the range of qr_1 with $1 \leq qr_1 \leq 2$ and coincide in the range of wave number $2 < qr_1 \leq 10$. So, it was observed that there is no significant effect of the impedance parameter ratio of $\frac{Z_1}{Z_2}$ on elastic wave propagation in a micropolar elastic solid.

The effect impedance parameter ratio of $\frac{Z_1}{Z_2}$ on-stretch and micropolarity is shown in Figures 6 and 7. From these figures, it is observed that the wave frequencies vanish in micropolar and microstretch solids with impedance boundary conditions or empty boundary conditions in the range of small wave numbers $1 \leq qr_1 \leq 2$. The frequencies in micro-stretch elastic solids with an empty boundary are slightly higher than the frequencies in micropolar elastic solids with an empty boundary in the range of wave numbers $2 < qr_1 \leq 3$. It is seen that very high frequencies in a micropolar elastic solid of empty boundary are higher than micro-stretch solids of empty boundary in the wave number range $3 < qr_1 \leq 10$.

Fig 4. Variation of Frequency versus Wave number for different Impedance ratios in Micropolar solid

Fig 5. Variation of Frequency versus Wave number for empty boundary and different Impedance ratios in Micropolar solid

Fig 6. Variation of Frequency versus Wave number for empty boundary and different Impedance ratios in Micropolar solid and Micropolar with stretch solid

Fig 7. Variation of Frequency versus Wave number for empty boundary in Micropolar solid and Micropolar with stretch solid

4 Conclusion

The basic equations and material relationships of displacements, micro rotations, and micro stretch are converted into cylindrical coordinates (r, θ, z) and solved with the traditional "plane harmonic solution" method. Macro displacements, micro rotations, and micro stretch components are derived analytically. The analytical results were applied to explain a particular numerical example. From the analytical results and numerical example, the following observations are made:

- Two types of wave frequencies are derived analytically in a micropolar with a micro stretch cylindrical rod under the impedance boundary. The relations coincide with Rayleigh wave frequency relations for large values of wave number.
- The dispersion relations of elastic waves in a micropolar with micro stretch cylindrical rod under non-impedance boundary conditions coincide with Tomar's⁽¹²⁾ dispersion relations of an empty cylindrical bore.
- Elastic wave frequency relations along a micropolar cylindrical rod with and without impedance boundary conditions also coincide with Tomar's⁽¹²⁾ frequency relations in a micropolar empty cylindrical bore.
- Elastic wave speeds are proportional to the impedance parameter ratio $\frac{Z_1}{Z_2}$ in micro stretch cylindrical rod.
- High speed elastic waves occur in a micropolar cylindrical rod under impedance and non-impedance boundary conditions.
- There is no significant effect of the ratio $\frac{Z_1}{Z_2}$ on elastic wave speed in micropolar cylindrical rod.
- The speed of elastic waves vanishes in micropolar and micro stretch cylindrical rods with and without impedance boundary conditions in the range of small wave number.

The Significance and future research of the study

The analytical results of the study are very helpful for the researchers working in physics and different engineering fields. The graphical results of the discussed model are essential for the authors of mechanics. The concept of impedance boundary conditions is useful in electromagnetic and acoustics. Pathologists are very interested in the study of elastic waves or vibrations in "Ultrasound scanning" to diagnose different diseases of the human body in real life. All musical instruments are also working with this type of wave.

This article may be helpful because one can derive the dispersion relations and impedance boundary parameters.

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